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ОЛИЙ ВА ЎРТА МАХСУС ТАЪЛИМ ВАЗИРЛИГИ**

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***«ИННОВАЦИОН ҒОЯЛАР, ИШЛАНМАЛАР АМАЛИЁТГА: муаммолар, тадқиқотлар
ва ечимлар»***

Халқаро онлайн илмий-амалий анжуман

***«ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ, РАЗРАБОТКИ В ПРАКТИКУ: проблемы, исследования
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«ИННОВАЦИОН ҒОЯЛАР, ИШЛАНМАЛАР АМАЛИЁТГА:

Муаммолар, тадқиқотлар ва ечимлар»

Халқаро илмий-амалий онлайн анжуман материаллари тўплами

(2021 йил 21 апрель, Андижон).

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MODELS OF SOCIETY IN THE WORKS OF AMERICAN SCIENCE FICTION WRITERS

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the features of the societies created in the works of Lyon Sprague de Camp “Lest Darkness Fall” (1939), Isaac Asimov “Foundation” (1951-1953) and Orson Scott Card “Empire” (2006). It is revealed that most of these models of societies have been created following the example of the Roman Empire, and main heroes fight ignorance and act in the name of technical progress.*

Keywords: *science fiction, model of society, Camp, Asimov, Card.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada Leon Spreg de Kampning “Zulmatning qulashi” (1939), Isaak Azimovning “Tashkilot” (1951-1953) va Orson Skot Kardning “Imperiya” (2006) asarlarida yaratilgan jamiyat modellarining xususiyatlarini tahlil qilinadi. Ushbu modellarning aksariyati Rim imperiyasi misolida yaratilganligi va bosh qahramonlari texnik taraqqiyot yo'lida harakat qilishlari va jaholatga qarshi kurashishlari aniqlandi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ilmiy fantastika, jamiyat modeli, Kamp, Azimov, Kard.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье автор анализирует особенности моделей обществ, созданных в произведениях Леона Спрега де Кампа «Падение тьмы» (1939), Айзека Азимова «Основание» (1951-1953) и Орсона Скотта Карда «Империя» (2006). Выявлено, что большинство этих моделей созданы по примеру Римской империи, а главные герои действуют во имя технического прогресса и борются с невежеством.*

Ключевые слова: *научная фантастика, модель общества, Камп, Азимов, Кард.*

The concept of creating a model of society is at the heart of nearly all serious science fiction books. Most of them represent such subgenres as social science fiction, utopia (dystopia), satirical science fiction, space opera etc. It is interesting that among all models of the future societies, the most popular among writers was a model similar to the model of the Roman Empire. In fact, the concept of empire in science fiction was first explored from a literary point of view by Patricia Kerslake in his work “Science Fiction and Empire” [1, 47].

In the works of American science fiction writers, there are examples of societies built on the basis of existing ones (alternative reality, utopia / dystopia), on the basis of empires created for protection or, conversely, to conquest (space opera) or as a result of the struggle for survival (apocalyptic / post-apocalyptic

science fiction). Ideologically and thematically, the values associated with empires are often positioned as negative. The empire oppresses the people, invades the territories of weaker rivals, thrives on corruption and survives only by virtue of its strength. Consequently, positive aspects are also noted, among them are – stability, potentially high opportunities for the development of science, a fairly high standard of living of at least some segments of the population. Of course, science fiction writers raise different problems, depending on the author's intention, the chosen subgenre, and the writer's personal style.

It is impossible to cover all the books suitable for the role of the object of our research in such a small scale article, therefore, three works were selected, for the creation of which their authors were inspired by the history of the Roman Empire: the novel “Lest Darkness Fall” (1939) by Lyon Sprague de Camp, the trilogy “Foundation” (1951-1953) by Isaac Asimov and “Empire” (2006) by Orson Scott Card.

In the novel “Lest Darkness Fall”, the Roman Empire of 535 is described, where the archaeologist Martin Padway from Italy of 1938 finds himself in an unknown way. Padway uses all the knowledge and skills of his time to fight the arrival of the dark ages and prevent the collapse of civilization. There are also interesting parallels that the author draws between the Roman Empire of 535 and Italy of 1938, which is ruled by Mussolini, who believes in the reincarnation of Julius Caesar. The author of the novel makes such a comparison for a certain reason – the Roman Empire before its collapse and a fascist state that cannot have a future. While the author himself in the introduction to his collection of short stories “The Wheels of If, and Other Science Fiction” (1948), insists that the novel “Lest Darkness Fall” is no more than entertainments, that “social significance is just the thing I studiously avoid in the story”. He goes on to say, “these yarns are meant purely to amuse and entertain, and neither to instruct, nor to incite, nor to improve” [2, 5]. In general, Lyon Sprague de Camp’s description of the Roman Empire is quite detailed, the focus in most of the plot is on specific actions of one or two characters.

A completely different picture can be seen in Isaac Asimov’s trilogy. The author’s desire to show the reader as much general picture of the society as it is possible, leads to the fact that a fairly large volume of the work is devoted to descriptions of the empire, its functions, historical references (which are given in the form of the so-called “Galactic Encyclopedia”). Asimov’s trilogy is based on “The History of the Decline and Fall of the Roman Empire” (1776-1788) written by the English historian Edward Gibbon. Although the presence of several worlds at once allowed Asimov to rely on other works, among which critics call the “Decline of Europe” (1918-1922) by German philosopher Oswald Spengler and

the fundamental historical work in 12 volumes “Comprehension of History” (1934-1961) written by English historian, sociologist, philosopher and cultural scientist Arnold Joseph Toynbee. Undoubtedly, on the pages of his trilogy Asimov creates an impressive universe. Unlike the novel “Lest Darkness Fall”, in Asimov’s trilogy, not everything boils down to the actions of the main character, whole organizations, states, and even whole planets operate there.

In addition, there are also common features in both works. Thus, historical laws are valid both in de Camp’s novel and in Asimov's trilogy. In addition, the idea of the fall of any major civilization is supported by both authors. The belief of both authors in history as a science is strong. In a sense, Asimov’s “psychohistory” is nothing more than a mathematical expression of the psychology of humanity, that is, a mathematical translation of the works of Spengler and Toynbee.

The situation is somewhat different in the novel “Empire” by Orson Scott Card. With a strong political focus, the novel is dedicated to the fall of the modern empire represented by the United States. The writer sees the cause of the collapse in the shortsightedness of politicians, in the incitement of bloody conflicts, in the vacuum of real power, in the stupidity of the military and the cunning of selfish corporations. As the writer himself notes, “I used to be sure that civil wars are possible only in countries like Rwanda, Bosnia, Serbia, Sudan. And the script presented in the novel at first seemed implausible. But if you really think about the rationale, anything can be made realistic... I have polarized today’s political situation in America to the extreme point. And when I did this, I realized that a civil war could start anywhere, even in our country” [3, 77].

Thus, in all three works under consideration, there is an empire in one form or another, events are described that can both lead to its collapse and save it from complete disintegration. The actors, most often, are both the leaders of the empire and the first persons of the state, as well as ordinary people who are in a difficult situation and trying to do everything possible to direct the process of historical development in the most favorable direction for mankind.

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